

VIEWS OF FOREIGN PSYCHOLOGISTS ON THE DEFECTS OBSERVED IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The purpose of physical education of children with mental retardation is to strengthen their health, develop proper physical development and movement skills. Systematic educational process creates favorable conditions for children's harmonious development. Mentally retarded children have somatic weakness compared to their peers, lagging behind in physical development, posture and movement defects. Special tasks aimed at eliminating movement defects and lagging behind physical development of mentally retarded children determine the specific characteristics of physical education of these children. This article presents the opinions of foreign psychologists about the changes in the psyche of children who are behind in their development, their intelligence, psychological processes and imagination.*

Keywords: *anomalous, oligophrenopsychology, typhlopsychology, deaf psychology, sensor, inclusive education, psychocorrection, psychorehabilitation.*

Introduction

In our country, serious attention is being paid to the issues of children with developmental disabilities being brought up in the national spirit, mentally, morally and physically matured, ready for social life in society at the level of independent and mature citizens, along with their healthy peers.

Establishment of specialized state educational institutions (preschool educational organizations, schools, boarding schools) (hereinafter, specialized educational institutions) for children with physical, mental, sensory or psychic disabilities and placement of children there, as well as the procedure for organizing inclusive education, its activities are implemented in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 638 adopted on October 12, 2021 " "On approval of normative legal documents on education of children with special educational needs".

In the last decade of the 20th century, important changes took place in most countries related to the development of integration and the establishment and development of new relations in the state and society towards children with limited opportunities, special attention, and disabled children. At present, a system of institutions providing comprehensive support to mentally retarded children of preschool age and their parents is operating in our republic. Such institutions operate in the healthcare, social protection and education systems, in the form of non-governmental organizations. These include orphanages, rehabilitation centers for disabled children, special pre-school educational institutions, special (correctional) schools, boarding schools and their special camps, etc.

Literature review

Physical education is one of the departments of the program of education of mentally retarded children of preschool age in a special preschool educational institution. The goal of

physical education of children with mental retardation is to improve their health, develop proper physical development and movement skills. Systematic educational process creates favorable conditions for children's harmonious development. Mentally retarded children have somatic weakness compared to their peers, lagging behind in physical development, posture and movement defects. Special tasks aimed at eliminating movement defects and lagging behind physical development of mentally retarded children determine the specific characteristics of physical education of these children. Physical training is the main means of teaching mentally retarded children to move properly. With the help of basic movements (walking, running, jumping, throwing a ball, hanging), children develop vital movements. Acquiring movement skills has a positive effect on the child's physical and mental development, correction of defects, and the educational process.

The possibility and necessity of studying mentally retarded children, the need to educate and upbringing them, is inextricably linked with the development of medicine, psychiatry and psychology. At the end of the 18th century, at the beginning of the 19th century, certain positive views on the treatment, upbringing, and education of mentally retarded children appeared and began to take shape. It is worth mentioning that the issues of education of the mentally retarded first started with children with severe mental disabilities. The study, treatment, and education of children with relatively mild mental retardation appeared a little later, after the second half of the 19th century. In 1858, in foreign pedagogical literature, N.A. Dobrolyubov revealed the specific characteristics of a mentally retarded child. He showed that "low activity", "slow perception", "predominance of dry memorization", "uniform actions", "poor adaptation to new situations", "inability to use knowledge correctly" are typical features of mentally retarded children.

In the second half of the 19th century, at the beginning of the 20th century, a number of treatment and educational institutions were opened for the study, treatment, education and upbringing of mentally retarded children. In 1910, brother and sister Postovsky opened auxiliary classes for mentally retarded children at the elementary school. They also organized an experimental psychological office to study children. In 1911, the Institute of Child Psychology and Neuropathology was founded by the doctor-psychiatrist, professor G.I. Rossolimo. Here, the unique aspects of the psyche of mentally retarded children began to be studied. Since the 1920s, special psychology, especially the psychology of mentally retarded children, has been included in the education system as an independent science. Since then, this problem has been included in the system of affairs of state importance, and special attention has been paid to it. In 1925, the Institute of Experimental Defectology was established in Moscow. Under the leadership of L.S. Vygotsky (1896-1934), regular and consistent study of mentally retarded children was started. Great psychologist L.S. Vygotsky left a huge theoretical legacy in the field of special psychology. He is rightfully considered the founder of oligophrenopsychology. In 1935, L.V. Zankov began to manage the laboratory studying the psychology of mentally retarded children. The Institute of Experimental Defectology, which existed in 1943, was transformed into the Institute of Scientific Investigation of Defectology. The institute was headed by T.A. Vlasova until 1985.

According to L. S. Vygotsky, higher mental functions are a product of historical development and have a complex structure. This feature has a social character, and it includes not only higher mental functions in a person, but also elementary mental processes, that is, phonemic hearing, hearing voices, etc. Social experience, which leads to the emergence of complex forms of mental activity, cannot be considered as a process of acquisition of ready-made content. The

acquisition of social experience by the child is not only the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and cultural competencies, but also includes the formation of the child's personality, needs, and motives. Acquiring social experience is carried out in the active activities of the child, that is, in subject, educational, communication and game processes. The formation of higher mental functions plays an important role in children's interaction with adults in the early stages of development. The development of mental functions goes through several stages, and after that they become a complex mental process. All complex forms of mental activity (voluntary attention, logical memory, abstract thinking, etc.) have an indirect structure, in which speech plays a leading role. Even when objects and events do not exist, words take their place and represent the passage of any psychological process and become a part of its structure. Speech raises the structure and implementation of higher mental functions to a new, even higher level.

According to S. L. Rubinstein, "the relationship between the organ structure and its function is not one-way, the function does not depend on the organ structure, but the organ structure also depends on its function".

An important aspect of the formation of higher mental functions is the organization of symbolic activity, acquisition of the word sign. At first, the sign participates as an external, auxiliary factor. L.S. Vygotsky stated that each mental function goes through two stages in its development: the first "interpsychological" stage, in which the function is manifested as a relationship between people, and in the second stage - an internal, intrapsychological process. Higher mental functions are formed over the years. It is born with speech communication and ends with a complete symbol of activity (symbolic activity). The child's mental development and personality formation are inextricably linked with education and training processes. Thus, higher mental functions are seen as a complex process in psychology. Speech plays a decisive role in the formation of higher mental functions. P.K. Anokhin's concept of functional systems is used to explain psychophysiological mechanisms. A.R. According to Luria, the functional system is formed when the child is not ready at birth, but when his mental functions interact with objects and materials.

A functional system is a dynamic structure that combines a number of anatomical and physiological structures to perform a single task and is located in different nervous systems. Psychologists (A.R. Luria, A.N. Leontiev) have consistently emphasized that the physiological basis of higher mental functions is not the central nervous system or its individual parts, but the joint functioning of the functional system in the cerebral cortex. In the course of the child's life, the formation of this functional system gradually acquires a complex character, and the functional dependence is strengthened. This scientific regulation changed the ideas about the development of the human psyche. From the researches of physiologists and psychologists, we can see that the maturity of individual functional systems is not the same in a certain period of development: some systems have already been formed, and some are still being formed. Each functional system, even individual zones, has its own development program, but they work as a whole. In each young age, a certain functional system must be at the level of maturity, otherwise the activities of these systems cannot be carried out in a mutual relationship (L.O. Badalyan). Thus, mental processes and personality characteristics are not considered to be the result of maturity in separate parts or zones of the brain. They accumulate during ontogeny and depend on the child's social development situation. L.S. Vygotsky summarized the work of his predecessors (G.Y. Troshin, A.S. Griboyedov, E. Segen, M. Montessori, etc.) and developed the concept of anomalous

development. The basis of this concept is the cultural-historical theory of psychological development, which L.S. Vygotsky developed by studying the normal characteristics of development. The main features of L.S. Vygotsky's concept of anomalous development have not lost their importance even now.

They were developed in the works of T.A. Vlasova, J.L. Shif, V.L. Lubovsky, V.V. Lebedinsky, Ye.M. Mastjukova and other scientists in the 50s and 90s of the 20th century.

G. Y. Troshin put forward the idea about the general laws of normal and anomalous development, which we can see in the later works of many researchers (T. A. Vlasova, J. LShif, V. I. Lubovsky). L.S. Vygotsky explained the general laws of normal and anomalous development and stated that the social nature of mental development is common to them: pedagogical influence is the source of formation of higher mental functions in both normal and abnormal development. However, a number of regularities are distinguished that are not observed in normally developing children, but occur in children with developmental disabilities. In the works of T. A. Vlasova, V. I. Lubovsky, the general laws of anomalous developers are presented in a single system. L.S. Vygotsky's ideas about the systematicity of the structure of defects allowed him to divide them into two groups according to their anomalous development. This is a primary defect caused by the biological nature of the disease, a secondary defect that occurs in the child's social development and interactions with the environment.

According to J.I. Shifing, another law of anomalous development is changes in the development of the child's personality. Lack of mood, fear of social interaction, fear, low self-esteem, anxiety are the main qualities of such a person. Such disorders are caused by improper family upbringing and improper organization of education. Changes in communication skills disrupt children's speech, and as a result, the role of non-verbal means of communication increases. Deficiencies in the ability to receive and process data, V. I. Lubovsky said, reduce the volume and speed of received data, and prevent the storage and use of information. Another pattern of anomalous development is the disorder of speech activity, which is manifested in the inability to express speech indirectly.

Research Methodology

Inability to receive and process information, difficulties in communication, inability to remember materials hinder development in the formation of thinking, generalization and differentiation. All of these deficiencies in imagination and speech are always insufficient for children with these problems to perceive the environment, to retain their knowledge in their imagination. However, in combination with the specific characteristics of a child with a developmental disability, which consists of difficulties in adapting to the environment and teaching, there are also positive laws. One of them was noted by L.S. Vygotsky as a potential opportunity for the formation of the psyche of children with disabilities in the form of the proximal zone of development.

Another law was expressed by V. I. Lubovsky during the study of verbal control of children's actions. He showed the possibility of developing new conditional relationships without speech participation or partially expressed by words. Thus, the defective development has the laws of compensating both the lag in the formation of the psyche and the disorder.

A two-stage experiment was conducted to study the mental abilities of children educated in secondary "A" and "B" groups of the preschool educational organization in the experimental work of the research. Among these groups, we took group "A" as the control group, and group "B" as

the experimental group. At the first stage, children's perceptions of things were studied by giving the children the projective method "Find the missing thing in the picture". We evaluated each group participant in the "5" rating system, taking into account the time spent. The obtained results are shown in the table below.

PRE-EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

Middle "A"-class control group

Middle "B"-class experimental group

experimental group	control group
5 score – 8 - 25 %	5 score – 7 - 23 %
4 score – 15 - 47 %	4 score – 14 - 47 %
3 score – 7 - 22 %	3 score – 7 - 23 %
2 score – 2 - 6 %	2 score – 2 - 7 %

32g`100 %	30g`100 %
32-x	30-x
$Xg\`{(23*100)G\`32}$	$Xg\`{(21*100)G\`30}$
$Xg\`71,8$	$Xg\`70,0$

Conclusion/Recommendations

Based on the results of the conducted research, it can be concluded that it is necessary to develop methods of using new pedagogical technologies and introduce them to education in order to eliminate various shortcomings of children who are lagging behind in their development. The introduction of differentiated and integrated type of education in training children who are lagging behind in their development is a very effective process for the students. The reason is that the teacher gives more information to the pupils without any difficulty in a short period of time, and the pupils get more knowledge, their thinking skills grow even more. Children quickly understand the connections and complements between disciplines and subjects, sections in the textbook. RRS

allows for timely identification of children, correct and accurate diagnosis of their deficiencies, creates conditions for special education, getting positive results in teaching and upbringing of children, and is sufficient for children's future development and successful schooling.

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